

ON THE MEAN VALUE OF THE *SCBF* FUNCTION

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Abstract The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method to study the asymptotic properties of the *SCBF* function on simple numbers, and give an interesting asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords: *SCBF* function; Mean value; Asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction

In reference [1], the Smarandache Sum of Composites Between Factors function $SCBF(n)$ is defined as: The sum of composite numbers between the smallest prime factor of n and the largest prime factor of n . For example, $SCBF(14)=10$, since $2 \times 7 = 14$ and the sum of the composites between 2 and 7 is: $4 + 6 = 10$. In reference [2]: A number n is called simple number if the product of its proper divisors is less than or equal to n . Let A denotes set of all simple numbers. That is, $A = \{2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 17, 19, 21, \dots\}$.

According to reference [1], Jason Earls has studied the arithmetical properties of $SCBF(n)$ and proved that $SCBF(n)$ is not a multiplicative function. For example, $SCBF(14 \times 15) = 10$ and $SCBF(14) \times SCBF(15) = 40$. He also got that if i and j are positive integers then $SCBF(2^i \times 5^j) = 4$, $SCBF(2^i \times 7^j) = 10$, etc. In this paper, we use the elementary method to study the mean value properties of $SCBF(n)$ on simple numbers, and give an interesting asymptotic formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. Let $x \geq 1$, A denotes the set of all simple numbers. Then we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in A}} SCBF(n) = B \frac{x^3}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^2 x}\right),$$

where $B = \frac{1}{3} \sum_p \frac{1}{p^3}$ is a constant, \sum_p denotes the summation over all primes.

§2. Some Lemmas

To complete the proof of the theorem, we need the following lemmas:

Lemma 1. For any prime p and positive integer k , we have the asymptotic formula

$$SCBF(p^k) = 0.$$

Proof. (See reference [1]).

Lemma 2. Let $n \in A$, then we have $n = p$, or $n = p^2$, or $n = p^3$, or $n = pq$ four case, where p, q denote the distinct primes.

Proof. First let n be a positive integer, $p_d(n)$ is the product of all positive divisors of n , that is, $p_d(n) = \prod_{d|n} d$. $q_d(n)$ is the product of all positive divisors of n but n . That is, $q_d(n) = \prod_{d|n, d < n} d$. Then from the definition of $p_d(n)$ we know that

$$p_d(n) = \prod_{d|n} d = \prod_{d|n} \frac{n}{d}.$$

So from this formula we have

$$p_d^2(n) = \prod_{d|n} d \times \prod_{d|n} \frac{n}{d} = \prod_{d|n} n = n^{d(n)}.$$

where $d(n) = \sum_{d|n} 1$. Then we may immediately get $p_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}}$ and

$$q_d(n) = \prod_{d|n, d < n} d = \frac{\prod_{d|n} d}{n} = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2} - 1}.$$

By the definition of the simple numbers, we get $n^{\frac{d(n)}{2} - 1} \leq n$. Therefore, we have

$$d(n) \leq 4.$$

This inequality holds only for $n = p$, or $n = p^2$, or $n = p^3$, or $n = pq$ four cases. This completes the proof of Lemma 2.

Lemma 3. For any distinct prime p and q , we have the asymptotic formula

$$SCBF(pq) = \frac{q^2}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\ln q}\right) - \frac{p^2}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\ln p}\right) + O\left(\frac{q^2}{\ln^2 q}\right).$$

Proof. From the definition of $SCBF(n)$, we have

$$SCBF(pq) = \sum_{p < n < q} n - \sum_{p < q_1 < q} q_1,$$

where q_1 is a prime. Using the Abel's Identity [3] and note that the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} n^\alpha = \frac{x^{\alpha+1}}{\alpha+1} + O(x^\alpha)$$

we can get

$$\begin{aligned}
 SCBF(pq) &= \sum_{p < n < q} n - \sum_{p < q_1 < q} q_1 \\
 &= \sum_{p < n \leq q-1} n - \sum_{p < q_1 \leq q-1} q_1 \\
 &= \sum_{n \leq q-1} n - \sum_{n \leq p} n - \sum_{p < q_1 \leq q-1} q_1 \\
 &= \frac{(q-1)^2}{2} - \frac{(p-1)^2}{2} + O(q) - (q-1)\pi(q-1) + p\pi(p) \\
 &\quad + \int_p^{q-1} \pi(t) dt \\
 &= \frac{q^2}{2} - \frac{q^2}{2 \ln q} - \frac{p^2}{2} + \frac{p^2}{2 \ln p} + O\left(\frac{q^2}{\ln^2 q}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Lemma 3.

Lemma 4. For real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{pq \leq x} SCBF(pq) = B \frac{x^3}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^2 x}\right),$$

where p and q are two distinct primes, $B = \frac{1}{3} \sum_p \frac{1}{p^3}$ is a constant, and \sum_p denotes the summation over all primes.

Proof. From the definition of $SCBF(n)$ and Lemma 1, Lemma 3, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{pq \leq x} SCBF(pq) &= 2 \sum_{pq \leq x, p < q} SCBF(pq) - \sum_{p^2 \leq x} SCBF(p^2) \\
 &= 2 \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} SCBF(pq) \\
 &= \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} \left(q^2 - \frac{q^2}{\ln q} - p^2 + \frac{p^2}{\ln p} + O\left(\frac{q^2}{\ln^2 q}\right) \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Noting that $\pi(x) = \frac{x}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^2 x}\right)$, using Abel's Identity [3] we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} q^2 &= \pi\left(\frac{x}{p}\right) \frac{x^2}{p^2} - \pi(p) p^2 - 2 \int_p^{\frac{x}{p}} \pi(t) t dt \\
 &= \frac{x^3}{3p^3 \ln \frac{x}{p}} - \frac{p^3}{3 \ln p} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{p^3 \ln^2 \frac{x}{p}}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} \frac{q^2}{\ln q} &= A\left(\frac{x}{p}\right)f\left(\frac{x}{p}\right) - A(p)f(p) - \int_p^{\frac{x}{p}} A(t)f(t)' dt \\ &= \frac{x^3}{3p^3 \ln^2 \frac{x}{p}} - \frac{p^3}{3 \ln^2 p} - \frac{p^3}{9 \ln^3 p} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{p^3 \ln^3 \frac{x}{p}}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where $A\left(\frac{x}{p}\right) = \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} q^2$, $f(x) = \frac{1}{\ln x}$. From reference [3], we know that

$$\sum_{p \leq x} \frac{1}{p} = \ln \ln x + C + O\left(\frac{1}{\ln x}\right),$$

where C is a computable constant. And then we also get

$$\sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} p = \frac{x}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^2 x}\right)$$

and

$$\sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} p^3 = \frac{x^2}{2 \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x}\right).$$

Using the same method, we obtain

$$\sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{p}{\ln p} = \frac{2x}{\ln^2 x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^3 x}\right)$$

and

$$\sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{p^3}{\ln p} = \frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^3 x}\right).$$

Noting that $\frac{1}{1 - \frac{\ln p}{\ln x}} = 1 + \frac{\ln p}{\ln x} + \frac{\ln^2 p}{\ln^2 x} + \dots + \frac{\ln^m p}{\ln^m x} + \dots$, then we get the following two formulae:

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} q^2 \\ &= \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{x^3}{3p^3 \ln \frac{x}{p}} - \frac{p^3}{3 \ln p} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{p^3 \ln^2 \frac{x}{p}}\right) \right) \\ &= \frac{x^3}{3 \ln x} \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{1}{p^3} \left(1 + \frac{\ln p}{\ln x} + \frac{\ln^2 p}{\ln^2 x} + \dots \right) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{3} \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{p^3}{\ln p} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^2 x} \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{1}{p^3} \left(1 + 2\frac{\ln p}{\ln x} + 3\frac{\ln^2 p}{\ln^2 x} + \dots \right)\right) \\ &= C_1 \frac{x^3}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^2 x}\right); \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} \frac{q^2}{\ln q} \\
 = & \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{x^3}{3p^3 \ln^2 \frac{x}{p}} - \frac{p^3}{3 \ln^2 p} - \frac{p^3}{9 \ln^3 p} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{p^3 \ln^3 \frac{x}{p}}\right) \right) \\
 = & \frac{x^3}{3 \ln^2 x} \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{1}{p^3} \left(1 + 2 \frac{\ln p}{\ln x} + 3 \frac{\ln^2 p}{\ln^2 x} + \dots \right) - \frac{1}{3} \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{p^3}{\ln^2 p} \\
 & - \frac{1}{9} \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{p^3}{\ln^3 p} + O\left(\sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{x^3}{p^3 \ln^3 \frac{x}{p}}\right) \\
 = & C_2 \frac{x^3}{\ln^2 x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x}\right),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $C_1 = C_2 = \frac{1}{3} \sum_p \frac{1}{p^3}$.

So we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2 \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} SCBF(pq) \\
 = & \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} \left(q^2 - \frac{q^2}{\ln q} - p^2 + \frac{p^2}{\ln p} + O\left(\frac{q^2}{\ln^2 q}\right) \right) \\
 = & \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} q^2 - \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} \frac{q^2}{\ln q} - \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} p^2 \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} 1 \\
 & + \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{p^2}{\ln p} \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} 1 + O\left(\sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < q \leq \frac{x}{p}} \frac{q^2}{\ln^2 q}\right) \\
 = & B \frac{x^3}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^2 x}\right),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $B = \frac{1}{3} \sum_p \frac{1}{p^3}$. This proves Lemma 4.

§3. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we complete the proof of Theorem. According to the definition of simple numbers and Lemma 2, we have

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in A}} SCBF(n)$$

$$= \sum_{p \leq x} SCBF(p) + \sum_{p^2 \leq x} SCBF(p^2) + \sum_{p^3 \leq x} SCBF(p^3) + \sum_{pq \leq x} SCBF(pq).$$

And then, using Lemma 1 and Lemma 4 we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in A}} SCBF(n) &= \sum_{pq \leq x} SCBF(pq) \\ &= B \frac{x^3}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^2 x}\right). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem.

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References

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